

GRAPHENE FILLED EPOXY COATINGS FOR ENHANCED CORROSION PROTECTION

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ABSTRACT

The ability of graphene oxide derived fillers to enhance the moisture barrier performance of epoxy coating has been investigated. Films and coatings of virgin and modified graphene oxide (GO) were produced with different dispersion methods. Water vapour transmission rate (WVTR) was evaluated. Reduction in WVTR of GO/epoxy films were less than predicted and in one case, was higher than unfilled epoxy film. However, moisture barrier and corrosion protection performance were improved by reducing the graphene oxide. Films with reduced GO (rGO) have smaller WVTR while corrosion rate of rGO/epoxy coating was also lowered.

1. INTRODUCTION

Corrosion presents a constant threat to the integrity of oil & gas (O&G) production facilities. The cost of corrosion can be tremendous, and it has been estimated that it could amount to a significant portion of an industrialised nation's gross national product (GNP) [1].

In the oilfield, organic coatings are perhaps one of the most widely used methods to combat corrosion by forming a physical barrier between the steel substrate and the corrosive environment, *e.g.* seawater. However, organic coatings are not totally impervious to fluids so that over time and under particular operational conditions, the fluids would ingress into and penetrate through it thereby reaching the steel substrate that it is meant to protect. In the process, the coating performance may also be detrimentally affected, which would exacerbate the rate of permeation of the fluids. Hence the barrier performance of organic coatings against moisture and other corrosive species will directly dictate the effectiveness of the coating as a corrosion protection layer, especially in the long term and under extreme conditions. Graphene is hydrophobic and its membrane have been shown to be impermeable to moisture, amongst others. As a nanofiller in a polymer matrix, it increases the path of tortuosity of the permeation path. The filled structure can be idealised as a brick-and-mortar model. As depicted in Figure 1, the model shows that the barrier performance is dependent on the flake aspect ratio and loading, with the greatest reduction in permeability estimated at filler content of less than 1 vol% for high aspect ratio flakes [2], such as graphene. Graphene oxide (GO), on the other hand, is hydrophilic and, despite having exceptional barrier properties against non-polar liquids and gases, does not bode well with water in term of barrier performance. This suggests that GO based nanocomposites will make poor moisture barriers and, hence, exhibit poor anti-corrosion properties when used as a coating. The poor water vapour barrier property of GO is clearly proven in GO-only [2] membranes but its effect as a nanofiller within a polymer matrix is still unclear. In fact, in some instances, the addition of GO resulted in improved moisture barrier property of the nanocomposites. Similar findings were also reported by Rajabi *et al.* [3] for corrosion rates of GO nanocomposite coating. Epoxy coating with 0.125wt% GO resulted in a 7%

increase in rate of corrosion but 0.25wt% GO reduced corrosion rate by 60%. Hence, moisture barrier performance should not be used as the only indicator for corrosion resistance organic coatings, at least in the case of GO nanocomposites. However, this remains inconclusive since comparison between different published works is difficult due to the different chemicals and processes that used. Furthermore, in filled nanocomposite systems, apart from filler type, the reduction in permeability is also highly dependent upon concentration, filler aspect ratio and dispersion. Dispersion presents a major challenge because graphene and its derivatives all have a tendency to agglomerate due to their large specific surface area and poor dispersion in solvents [4].

In the current work, two-dimensional (2D) graphene oxide derived fillers are investigated for their ability to enhance the barrier performance of epoxy used as an organic coating. This paper will present results and findings from a study to investigate the moisture barrier property of GO, reduced GO (rGO) and modified GO epoxy nanocomposites prepared by different dispersion methods. The objective is to understand the effects of filler type (GO versus rGO) and loading on moisture barrier properties and corrosion resistance, while developing homogeneous dispersion of the nanoflakes.

Figure 1. Relationship between permeability of filled composite (P_c), unfilled matrix (P_m), flake aspect ratio and filler content, based on idealised "brick-and-mortar" model [5].

2. EXPERIMENTAL

GO, rGO and octadecylamine modified GO (ODA-GO) were prepared for this study. GO was prepared using an improved Hummer's method [6] in a jacketed glass reactor, and it was repeatedly centrifuged, washed and exfoliated with purified water. Alkyl functionalised GO was obtained by mixing octadecylamine (ODA) to aqueous dispersion of GO. The functionalised GO, *i.e.* ODA-GO, was extracted by vacuum filtration and washed with excess ethanol to remove unreacted ODA [7]. To produce rGO, freeze dried GO was thermally reduced in hydrogen/argon atmosphere at 900°C. The various nanoflakes were then analysed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), thermal gravimetry analysis (TGA) and Fourier transform infra-red (FTIR) spectroscopy.

GO, ODA-GO and rGO reinforced epoxy (*i.e.* D.E.R. 332, Sigma-Aldrich) were made by blending dried nanoflakes with epoxy using a Thinky planetary mixer. A separate set of GO/epoxy nanocomposites were also produced, by mixing aqueous GO solution with liquid bisphenol-A epoxy. Water was removed by slow evaporation at 80°C. Nanocomposites with up to 1wt% of nanofillers were considered in this work. The filled epoxy was mixed with polyetheramine (average Mn ~230, Sigma-Aldrich) hardener and degassed for 30 mins. The processing matrix is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of the processing methods used to produce nanoflakes for the present work.

Sample	Filler	Mixing method	Description
Aq-GO	GO	Overhead stirrer	Mix aq. GO with epoxy. Remove water by slow evaporation at 80°C.
ODA-GO	Modified GO	Overhead stirrer	Stir modified GO with epoxy resin.
GO	GO	Planetary mixer	Mix at 2000rpm.
rGO	Reduced GO	Planetary mixer	Mix at 2000rpm.

Figure 2. Epoxy nanocomposites disc with different filler content for WVTR testing. Assembled aluminium cup is shown on the right.

Water vapour transmission rate (WVTR) and electrochemical corrosion measurements were carried out on films, *viz.* thin sheets of cast resins with nominal thickness of 200µm, and coatings, *viz.* thicker sheets of resins of nominally 20 µm in thickness, respectively. The cast resin sheets were cured at 40°C for 24 hours followed by postcuring at 80°C for 3 hours.

WVTR was measured using the gravimetric cup method, according to ASTM E96 [8]. Test samples films were secured over the opening of the cup with a ring and bolts, thus sealing in the calcium chloride absorbent, which was filled inside the cup prior to that (see Figure 1). The assembled cups were then placed inside a climatic test chamber that maintains an environment of 38°C and 90% relative humidity (RH). Cups were removed from chamber and weighed at 24-hour intervals for 7 to 10 days. WVTR was determined from the slope of mass gained versus time.

The corrosion protection performance of the nanocomposites coating were evaluated using the Tafel electrochemical test method. Mild steel plates coated with the test sample resin were immersed in 3.5% sodium chloride solution at 50°C for 5 days. Tests were carried out in a Faraday cage using a paint test cell (PTC1, Gamry Instrument) clamped over the coated plate. The cell contains a graphite counter electrode, saturated calomel reference electrode and 3.5% sodium chloride electrolyte. Corrosion rates were calculated from Faraday's Law using Equation 1, according to ASTM G102 [9]

$$CR = K_1 \frac{i_{cor}}{\rho} EW \quad \dots (1)$$

where CR = corrosion rate in mm/year,
 $K_1 = 3.27 \times 10^{-3}$ mm g/µA cm year,
 i_{cor} = corrosion current density in µA/cm²,
ρ = density of substrate in g/cm³,
EW = equivalent weight of the corroding metal.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Size distribution of the flakes used in this work, as shown in Figure 3, was measured from SEM images of 80-90 different flakes, as shown in Figure 3. Average lateral size of the GO and rGO flakes were $5.5 \pm 4.3 \mu\text{m}$ and $6.5 \pm 3.6 \mu\text{m}$, respectively, while the largest lateral flake sizes obtained were $26\mu\text{m}$ and $18\mu\text{m}$, as shown in Figure 4. The average thickness measured with AFM is 1.63nm .

Figure 3. Representative SEM images of (a) GO, and (b) rGO.

Figure 4. Maximum size distribution of the GO and rGO flakes.

Details of characterisation of ODA-GO have previously been reported by Leong *et al.* [7]. TGA measurements of ODA-GO showed reduced rate of mass loss compared to GO due to partial consumption of reactive oxygen containing groups during functionalization. However functionalization did not completely reduce the GO [7]. The thermal degradation of GO, ODA-GO and rGO in air is shown in Figure 5. The mass loss of ODA-GO is more gradual compared to GO. At temperatures below 180°C , adsorbed moisture and unreacted ODA was removed. Further mass loss up to 550°C is due to decomposition of the amine GO and remaining carbon bonds.

Figure 5. Representative plot of mass loss of flakes versus temperature, in air.

Figure 7 compares the WVTR of different dispersion method at 0.25wt% of filler content. The Aq-GO/epoxy and ODA-GO/epoxy films were found to be approximately 30% lower than the unfilled epoxy film. There were no significant difference in WVTR between the ODA-GO/epoxy and the (poorly dispersed) Aq-GO/epoxy films, despite the marked difference in flake dispersion. The worst performer was the GO/epoxy film, which had the most homogeneous nanoflakes distribution, showing an increase of 33% in WVTR. This rise in water vapour permeability could be due to formation of new permeation pathway between aggregated hydrophilic GO flakes. Similar phenomenon have been reported for hydrophilic clay/polymer films [4].

Figure 8 shows the WVTR for the GO/epoxy films with a filler content of up to 1wt%. The WVTR reached a maximum value before it dropped to the level of unfilled epoxy films. The rGO/epoxy films performed significantly better than their GO counterpart, demonstrating superior barrier against moisture of 30% reduction in WVTR, at just 0.1wt% loading (see Figure 9).

Figure 6. Distribution of (a) Aq-GO, (b) ODA-GO and (c) GO in epoxy (all micrographs were taken at magnification).

Figure 7. WVTR of 0.25wt% nanofiller/epoxy films (thickness normalised to 200 μ m) prepared by different methods (error bars represent standard deviation).

Figure 8. Averaged water vapour transmission rate of GO films (error bars represent standard deviation).

Figure 9. WVTR of 0.1wt% GO and rGO filled epoxy film.

Figure 10. Tafel diagram of different coatings after 5 days immersion in a 3.5wt% salt solution.

Tafel test was carried out on neat, GO and rGO filled epoxy coated steel plates. Coating thickness is between 16-25 μ m. The post cured coating plates were immersed in 50°C aqueous sodium chloride solution (3.5%) for 5 days prior to testing. Corrosion current density (i_{cor}) obtained from Tafel plots were used to calculate the corrosion rate of the substrate (see Figure 10). GO/Epoxy plate had the highest corrosion rate, which is 27% higher than neat epoxy coated plate. rGO/epoxy coating reduced the corrosion rate by 35% compared to neat epoxy (see Table 2). Coating blisters and corrosion spots were observed on the neat epoxy and GO/epoxy coated plates (Figure 11).

Table 2. Corrosion rate of uncoated plate, and neat epoxy, 0.5wt% GO and rGO/epoxy coated plates.

Coating	Corrosion rate (mm/year)
Uncoated	6.0×10^{-1}
Neat epoxy	7.0×10^{-4}
0.5wt% GO/Epoxy	8.9×10^{-4}
0.5wt% rGO/Epoxy	4.6×10^{-4}

Figure 11. Condition of (a) neat epoxy, (b) 0.5wt% GO/Epoxy and (c) rGO/epoxy coated steel plates after 5 day immersion in 50°C sodium chloride solution.

4. CONCLUSION

Epoxy based nanocomposite coatings and films were produced with graphene oxide (GO) derived nanofillers. Different methods were employed to disperse the flakes in epoxy. Coating performance was evaluated by measuring film water vapour transmission rates while corrosion rates were calculated from Tafel test of coated steel plates. All the GO/epoxy films tested produced smaller reduction in WVTR than predicted by theoretical model. The modified ODA-GO flakes easily disperses in epoxy resin but did not produce any significant improvement in moisture barrier property when compared to the more poorly dispersed Aq-GO system. Improving the dispersion of GO flakes by planetary mixing increased WVTR instead and significant reduction in WVTR was only achieved from rGO/epoxy films. Preliminary work using the Tafel method to evaluate corrosion performance of the nanocomposite films have shown rGO films, with its reduced WVTR, improved coating performance resulting reduction in corrosion rate of the underlying substrate. Epoxy films with 0.5wt% rGO nanofillers produced a 35% and 51% reduction in corrosion rate compared to neat epoxy and 0.5wt% GO filled coating, respectively. In conclusion, rGO has been demonstrated to be a suitable filler for moisture barrier films and anti-corrosion coating.

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